

Analysis and assessment of the quality indicators of the inpatient activity of the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” in the period 2013–2024

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Abstract

Hospital care, and inpatient activity in particular, is a key component of the health system, providing comprehensive treatment and highly specialized, continuous care for patients. This study tracks the main trends and dynamics in the quality indicators of inpatient activity at the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” during the period 2013–2024. The results show fluctuations determined by both the general healthcare environment and extraordinary factors, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, followed by a sustainable recovery of activity.

Keywords

assessment, dynamics, hospital, inpatient activity, quality indicators

Introduction

Hospital care is a major component of the healthcare system, providing diagnosis, treatment, rehabilitation, and monitoring of patients requiring continuous medical care and professional supervision in hospital settings. According to the World Health Organization (World Health Organization 2018), it is an integral part of comprehensive healthcare and includes all activities that are carried out in a stationary treatment regime by a doctor or under the supervision of a doctor. Hospitals are centers of highly specialized medical activity and concentrate a significant part of the human, financial, and technological resources in the system (World Health Organization 2017; Kirkov 2023).

In a national context, according to the Ministry of Health (MH 2022), hospital care is provided by medical institutions registered under the Law on Medical Institutions, which have the necessary structure, equipment, and staff to provide specialized medical care. It includes both emergency and planned hospitalizations, and the volume and quality of the activity are measured by a number of statistical indicators – total number of patients admitted, number of hospitalizations, average length of stay, bed utilization, bed turnover, and hospital mortality (Campbell et al. 2000; Busse et al. 2011; Law on medical institutions in the Republic of Bulgaria 2025).

In recent years, a number of factors – demographic changes, growing demand for health services, limited

resources, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic – have posed new challenges for hospital structures in Bulgaria. This requires a thorough analysis and objective assessment of their activities, which can serve as a basis for management decision-making and improving the organization of medical care (Kelley and Hurst 2006; Kirkov 2024; Mahomedradja et al. 2024).

Inpatient activity is a major component of hospital care and reflects the effectiveness of organization, the quality of services provided, and the degree of utilization of available resources. As noted by Aleksandrova et al. (2024), the effectiveness of inpatient activity is directly related to the rational use of bed capacity and human resources, which determines not only financial and economic results but also patients' access to quality treatment (Siciliani et al. 2013; Vodenitcharov and Borisov 2021).

According to an analysis by the European Commission (European Commission 2024), trends in hospital care in EU countries show a common goal – optimization of bed capacity and promotion of efficiency by reducing unnecessary hospitalizations and improving outpatient care. These changes are also reflected in Bulgaria, where the dynamics of hospital activity are influenced by both regulatory changes and socioeconomic factors.

According to Karpova and Zagoruychenko (2022), inpatient activity indicators – bed utilization, average length of stay, and bed turnover – serve as indicators of efficiency and allow for objective comparison between medical institutions. On the other hand, excessive length of stay or low bed turnover may signal inefficient use of resources or organizational problems.

In this context, the assessment of inpatient activity is a key tool for the management of medical institutions. It allows not only tracking the dynamics of hospitalizations but also identifying factors that affect the quality and effectiveness of medical care (WHO 2019, 2023). Conducting a systematic analysis of inpatient activity supports management decisions aimed at improving work organization, optimizing resources, and increasing patient satisfaction.

The purpose of this article is to examine and analyze the structure and dynamics of the quality indicators for the activity of the inpatient department of the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” during the period 2013–2024.

Materials and methodology of the research

The object of this scientific study is the structure and dynamics of the quality indicators for the activity of the inpatient ward of the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” during the period 2013–2024, as well as the factors influencing them.

The study was conducted based on reporting data and statistical information provided by the medical institution, including tables and graphs reflecting the dynamics of inpatient activity for the period 2013–2024. The analy-

sis used both absolute and relative indicators, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the volume, intensity, and effectiveness of hospital care.

A wide range of sociological, statistical, and documentary methods were used in conducting the study, as follows:

- descriptive statistical analysis – to present the current state and volume of activity;
- comparative and dynamic analysis – to study changes over time;
- graphical method – to visualize trends;
- calculation of average and relative values – to assess the efficiency and workload of the bed fund.

Results and discussion

The activities of the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” are organized into 25 specialized clinics, departments, and clinical and diagnostic structures. In order to make a realistic forecast and provide adequate guidelines for the development and activities of the medical institution in the coming years, a comprehensive analysis and assessment of the quality indicators for medical activity performed in the hospital's inpatient department should be conducted. This makes it possible to proactively diagnose problems facing the hospital and to formulate strategic priorities for its development.

On average, about 21,567.6 patients pass through the hospital annually. Against the background of a clearly expressed trend of increasing hospitalizations in Bulgaria as a whole, this study shows that the number of patients admitted to the medical institution is characterized by certain dynamics. In 2019, the highest number of patients was recorded, after which their number began to gradually decrease. In 2020, the number of patients treated decreased dramatically compared to the previous year – by 5,103 – which is probably due to the epidemiological situation in the country and the fact that medical care was sought mainly by patients with COVID-19. In 2022, there were 711 fewer patients compared to the beginning of the period. In 2023, the number of patients treated increased again and reached the level reported in 2019. In 2024, there were 21.8% more patients compared to 2013, which could be

Figure 1. Patients admitted to the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” for the period 2013–2024. **Source:** Financial Statement of University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD.

a function of increased demand for health services, potential catch-up of postponed hospitalizations related to chronic noncommunicable diseases, and restoration of the normal organization of work in the medical facility.

The number of bed days also gradually decreased over the years and, in 2020, was 32.7% lower than in 2013, reflecting reduced patient flow and lower intensity of treatment. The gradual decline until 2019 may be related to a smaller number of diseases, optimization of the treatment process, improved diagnostic capabilities, reduced complications after treatment, and more effective therapeutic methods being introduced, as well as the possibility of alternative forms of treatment, such as outpatient procedures, or a lower need for hospitalization. The sharp decline since 2020 corresponds to limited activity during the pandemic period.

However, in 2022, a gradual increase of 6.7% was reported, and in 2024, bed days increased by another 19.3% compared to 2020, which indicates that the hospital is expanding patient services or increasing the volume of treatment, with a higher need for medical services during this period.

Figure 2. Bed days spent at the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” for the period 2013–2024. **Source:** Financial Statement of University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD.

The average number of hospital beds is 464.5 and has remained stable over the analyzed period, especially over the last seven years, which suggests that there have been no significant changes in the capacity of the medical facility. Since the capacity of the inpatient unit does not change significantly, all variations in the other indicators are due to real changes in the volume and structure of the activity

Figure 3. Average annual number of beds at the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” for the period 2013–2024. **Source:** Financial Statement of University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD.

Table 1. Bed usability.

Year	Average utilization of one bed per year /in days/	Average utilization of one bed per year /in %/
2013	329.30	90.22
2014	302.50	82.88
2015	256.31	70.22
2016	259.30	70.85
2017	255.61	70.03
2018	250.05	68.51
2019	239.30	65.56
2020	198.64	54.27
2021	201.65	55.25
2022	211.92	58.60
2023	232.86	63.80
2024	236.96	64.74

Source: Financial Statement of the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD

performed. This provides greater reliability of the analysis and allows for a more precise assessment of efficiency. The stable number of beds also reflects the sustainability of the hospital as a tertiary medical care structure, which is characterized by a high degree of specialization and a constant patient flow.

As can be seen from the table, the utilization of hospital beds is not very high (on average about 68%, or 247.87 days), which indicates that the efficiency in hospital activity is relatively low. Over the analyzed period, it has been continuously decreasing, and in 2022 the utilization was lower by 32% compared to 2013. In 2023 and 2024, bed utilization increased by about 6%.

Figure 4. Bed turnover. **Source:** Financial Statement of the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD.

There is some dynamic change in bed turnover – at the beginning of the period there is a slight decrease, after which, between 2016 and 2019, the values gradually increase. In 2020 and 2021, bed turnover reaches its lowest values. However, in 2024, the number of patients treated per bed increases and is higher by 4.5 patients compared to 2013, which indicates higher efficiency in the use of the bed fund and a greater load on medical resources. This increase coincides with the rise in the number of patients treated in 2024 and shows that the hospital has managed to cope with the higher workload by making maximum use of its beds and resources.

The average length of stay is characterized by a downward trend, with its lowest values observed in the middle and at the end of the analyzed period. The trend of decreasing average length of stay is characteristic of the modern model of hospital care, in which early diagnosis, more effective treatment methods, and a multidisciplinary approach allow for faster patient recovery. In 2024, the average length of hospitalization decreased by 2.31 days compared to the beginning of the period, which can be interpreted as an indicator of faster patient recovery and a reduced need for prolonged hospitalization. This may be due to more effective treatment methods or the introduction of new technologies that shorten recovery time. Overall, the values approach the national average.

Figure 5. Average length of stay in hospital, days. **Source:** Financial Statement of the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD.

By reducing the average length of stay, bed turnover increases, meaning that hospital resources are used more efficiently and more patients can be treated with the same number of beds. On the other hand, there is a risk that reducing the average length of stay may lead to a decrease in the quality of medical and diagnostic activities. For this reason, a balance must be maintained between efforts to reduce the average length of stay and the need to preserve the quality of the diagnostic and treatment process.

Regarding hospital mortality, some dynamics are observed over the years, with a sharp increase in 2021, which is probably due to the high morbidity and complications

Figure 6. Hospital mortality, %. **Source:** Financial Statement of the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD.

associated with the COVID-19 pandemic. In 2022, hospital mortality decreased by more than half compared to the previous year. In 2023 and 2024, the downward trend continues, indicating a restoration of the normal profile of hospitalizations, better organization of treatment, and improved management of patients in critical condition.

Inferences and conclusion

The analysis of the quality indicators of inpatient activity at the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” for the period 2013–2024 reveals a distinct development of hospital activity, characterized by adaptability, organizational sustainability, and gradual improvement in the functioning of the treatment process. The data show that, despite serious external challenges – most notably the COVID-19 pandemic, which caused a sharp decrease in the volume of work and an increase in mortality – the hospital managed to stabilize its activity and restore key indicators to levels comparable to, or more favorable than, those in previous years. This demonstrates high flexibility of both the organizational structures and the professional teams working under conditions of extreme workload and clinical uncertainty.

After the most severe pandemic years, a steady trend toward recovery of inpatient activity has been observed, expressed in an increase in the number of treated patients and bed days, as well as in improvement of efficiency indicators such as bed utilization and bed turnover. In parallel, the reduction in the average length of stay and the normalization of hospital mortality after 2021 indicate optimization of the treatment process and timely implementation of good clinical practices. These results support the understanding that the hospital is successfully adapting to changing conditions in the healthcare system and is able to ensure sustainable quality of medical care.

An important factor contributing to the objective assessment of activity is the stable bed fund, which remains unchanged throughout the analyzed period. This allows the obtained results to be interpreted as a real reflection of dynamics in demand, organization, and efficiency of hospital care, rather than as a consequence of structural changes.

Therefore, the data from the present study show that the overall picture outlines a medical institution with sustainable capacity, stable organization, and consistent efforts to improve the quality and efficiency of provided hospital care. In this context, inpatient activity at the University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” can be defined as well organized, sustainable over time, and consistent with modern requirements of the health system.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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